

Ameliorative Effects of Aqueous Extract of Velvet Bean (*Mucuna Pruriens*) on Cadmium-induced Neurotoxicity in Frontal cortex of Male Adult Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Background: Cadmium (Cd) is a harmful environmental pollutant that induces neurotoxicity through oxidative stress and inflammation, particularly affecting the frontal cortex. Velvet Bean, a leguminous plant rich in antioxidants such as L-DOPA and flavonoids, offers a promising alternative for mitigating cadmium-induced neurotoxicity. This study aimed to evaluate the effects of aqueous extract of Velvet Bean on cadmium-induced neurotoxicity in the frontal cortex of adult male Wistar rats. **Materials and Methods:** Twenty-four rats were randomly assigned to four groups: normal control, cadmium only, cadmium + Velvet Bean extract, and Velvet Bean extract only. Cadmium chloride was administered intraperitoneally at a dose of 14 mg/kg body weight to induce neurotoxicity. Treatment began 72 hours post-induction and continued for four weeks, with Velvet Bean extract given orally at a dosage of 200 mg/kg bodyweight. **Results:** The cadmium-only group exhibited significant weight loss, decreased relative brain weight, and widespread histological degeneration, including necrotic pyramidal cells, reduced Nissl bodies, collagen deposition, and activated astrocytes, alongside elevated oxidative stress. In contrast, rats treated with *Mucuna Pruriens* extract showed significant improvements across all parameters compared to the cadmium-only group ($P < 0.05$). The extract preserved neuronal structure, maintained body and brain weights, and restored antioxidant enzyme levels, leading to reduced neuroinflammation and fibrosis. **Conclusion:** *Mucuna Pruriens* shows neuroprotective and antioxidative properties, indicating its potential for treating cadmium-induced neurotoxicity and other neurodegenerative disorders.

Introduction

Cadmium (Cd) is a harmful environmental pollutant that causes neurotoxicity primarily through oxidative stress and inflammation, with a particular impact on the frontal cortex. This brain region is critical for higher cognitive processes, including memory, attention, decision-making, and executive function [1,2]. Dysfunction in this area, induced by toxicants such as cadmium, leads to significant impairments in these cognitive abilities [3]. The effects of cadmium on the frontal cortex are largely mediated by oxidative stress, resulting in an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the brain's

endogenous antioxidant defense mechanisms [4,5]. Chronic exposure to cadmium has been linked to cognitive deficits, including attention disorders, poor decision-making, and memory impairments, which are commonly observed in neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's [6,7,8]. Current interventions for cadmium-induced neurotoxicity are limited, often resulting in significant side effects and proving ineffective in reversing neuronal damage [9]. Therefore, there is a pressing need for alternative therapeutic strategies that are both effective and safe to mitigate the harmful effects of cadmium on the brain.

More Information

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neurodegenerative disorder, neuroprotective and antioxidative properties, cadmium-induced neurotoxicity, Cadmium, environmental pollutant, *Mucuna pruriens*.

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Mucuna pruriens, a leguminous plant rich in L-DOPA and antioxidants, including flavonoids and various polyphenolic compounds such as tannins, alkaloids, and phenolic acids, exhibits strong antioxidant properties and has been shown to protect against oxidative stress [8]. This suggests that *Mucuna pruriens* may offer potential as a safer alternative for alleviating cadmium-induced neurotoxicity [10–12]. This study aimed to evaluate the ameliorative effects of the aqueous extract of *Mucuna pruriens* on cadmium-induced neurotoxicity in the frontal cortex of adult male Wistar rats.

Methods and Materials

Plant Material

Velvet Bean (*Mucuna pruriens*) was sourced from a seed farm in Chinsali, Zambia, and authenticated at the School of Natural Sciences, University of Zambia. The beans were air-dried, crushed, pulverized, and sifted to obtain a fine powder. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry was then used for extraction, resulting in a uniform preparation [12].

Animal Model and Housing

This research was conducted using 24 healthy male Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*), aged between 8 and 10 weeks, with body weights ranging from 160 to 200 grams. The animals were housed in four separate cages at the Department of Anatomy, Mulungushi University School of Medicine and Health Sciences, and maintained under standard conditions with access to regular feed and clean water.

Induction of Cadmium

The Wistar rats were subjected to overnight fasting and weighed. Cadmium chloride was dissolved in citric acid, and a single dose of 14 mg/kg body weight was administered intraperitoneally to the Cadmium-only and Cadmium + Velvet Bean extract groups [13].

Experimental Grouping

The rats were randomly distributed into four groups (n=6 per group) as follows:

- Group A: Normal control
- Group B: Cadmium only
- Group C: Cadmium + Velvet Bean extract
- Group D: Velvet Bean extract only

Administration of Velvet Bean Extract

The extract was dissolved in distilled normal saline daily, and administration was performed using an orogastric cannula for groups C and D Wistar rats at a dose of 200 mg/kg body weight each day for four weeks. Groups A and B Wistar rats were given 2 ml of normal saline [14].

Body Weight Assessment

Body weights of all rats were measured using a Venus VT 30 SL digital scale during the two weeks prior to cadmium induction and then weekly throughout the treatment period [15].

Relative Brain Weight Calculation

The relative brain weight was determined as a percentage of brain weight relative to the terminal body weight using a precision balance (Sony F3G model) [15].

Histological and Histochemical Analysis

At the conclusion of the study, the animals were euthanized, and the brain tissues were carefully excised. The tissues designated for histological studies were fixed in freshly prepared formal saline for 72 hours and then processed for routine histological examinations, stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) to observe changes in cellular morphology. Special stains, such as phosphotungstic acid haematoxylin (PTAH), Masson's trichrome, and toluidine blue stain, were utilized. Tissues for oxidative stress marker analyses (GSH, SOD, CAT, and MDA) were homogenized in 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4).

Photomicrography

Images of histological sections of the frontal cortex were captured using an Olympus microscope with an attached digital camera at the Department of Human Anatomy, Mulungushi University School of Medicine and Health Sciences, Livingstone Campus, Zambia.

Statistical Analysis

All data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical significance was determined using one-way ANOVA, and all graphical representations were prepared using Microsoft Excel. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Figure 1 illustrates the weekly changes in average body weight among the different groups. In weeks of acclimatization (week -1 and -2), the average body weights of rats was similar in all the groups when compared to each other, there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$). From week 0 and week 1, the average body weight of the rats in Cadmium only was maintained when compared other groups and was not significant ($p > 0.05$). From week 2 to week 4, the average body weight of the Cadmium only rats declined when compared to the other groups and was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). While, Cadmium + Velvet bean extract when compared to Velvet bean extract only and control was not significant ($p > 0.05$). Figure 2 illustrates the relative weight of the brain in the different groups of rats. The Cadmium only group showed a significant decrease in relative brain weight when compared to other groups at $p < 0.05$. The rats in the Cadmium + Velvet bean extract, showed slight decline, when compared to control and velvet bean extract only and they were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 1: Effect of an Aqueous Extract of Velvet bean on the Average Body Weight (g) on Weekly Basis. Data were Analyzed Using Mean ± SEM and P<0.05 Considered Significant

Figure 2: Relative Organ Weight. Data were Analyzed Using Mean ± SEM and p< 0.05 Considered Significant

Histological Findings

Hematoxylin and eosin stain of Frontal cortex

Figure 3 displays the histological sections of frontal cortex. The control and Velvet bean extract only groups exhibited normal histoarchitecture and numerous healthy pyramidal cells (figure 3A and 3D). The Cadmium + velvet bean extract group displayed a mixture of necrotic and normal cells indicating partial cellular damage (Figure 3C). The Cadmium only group revealed extensive necrosis, with most cells exhibiting severe damage (Figure 3B).

Figure 3: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. H&E Stain X400. A- Normal Control, B – Cadmium Only, C – Cadmium + Velvet Bean Extract, D – Velvet bean Extract Only. Arrow – Pyramidal Cells, Arrow Head is Necrotic Cells

Toluidine blue stain of Frontal cortex

Figure 4 demonstrates Nissl staining results. Control and Velvet Bean Only Groups showed well-preserved Nissl substances and normal pyramidal cell morphology (figure 4A and 4D). Moreover, the Cadmium + Velvet Bean Group showed preserved Nissl substances, suggesting partial protection against cadmium toxicity (figure 4C). The Cadmium Only Group exhibited sparse Nissl staining and widespread necrosis, indicating severe neuronal damage (figure 4B).

Figure 4: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. TDB Stain X400. A- Normal Control, B – Cadmium Only, C – Cadmium + Velvet Bean Extract, D – Velvet Bean Extract Only. Arrow – Pyramidal Cells, Arrow Head is Necrotic Cells

Masson Trichrome stain

Figure 5 illustrates collagen deposition in the frontal cortex. Control & Velvet Bean-Only revealed typical pyramidal cell distribution as seen in (figure 5A and 5D). While Cadmium-Only showed collagen deposition, suggesting fibrosis (figure 5B). Cadmium + Velvet Bean displayed healthy cells and reduced fibrosis, resembling the normal control (figure 5C).

Figure 5: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. Masson Stain X400. A- Normal Control, B – Cadmium Only, C – Cadmium + Velvet Bean Exact, D – Velvet Bean Extract Only. Black Arrow – Pyramidal Cells, Blue Arrow- Astrocyte, and Arrow Head is Deposition of Collagen

Phosphotungstic acid haematoxylin stain

Figure 6 demonstrates tissue elements of frontal cortex. Control & Velvet Bean-Only showed normal distribution of pyramidal cells and astrocytes (figure 6A and 6D). While Cadmium-Only exhibited necrotic pyramidal cells and increased astrocytes (Figure 6B). Cadmium + Velvet Bean demonstrated histoarchitecture similar to the normal control group (figure C), indicating recovery.

Figure 6: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. PTAH Stain X400. A- Normal Control, B – Cadmium Only, C – Cadmium + Velvet Bean Exact, D – Velvet Bean Extract Only. Black Arrow – Pyramidal Cells, Blue Arrow- Astrocyte, and Arrow Head is Necrotic Cells

Histochemical Study of the Frontal Cortex

Effect of an aqueous extract of Velvet Bean on the reduced glutathione (µg/mg protein)

Figure 7 depicts the activity of reduced glutathione (GSH) in the frontal cortex of various groups of Wistar rats. Notably, the cadmium only group exhibited the

lowest GSH activity, while as expected the normal control group exhibited the highest activity. When the cadmium + velvet bean extract group was compared with the normal control group and velvet bean extract only group, there was no statistical significant ($p>0.05$).

Figure 7: Frontal Cortex of Glutathione (GSH) Activity Level (µg/mg protein) at the End of Fourth Week. Data are Expressed as Mean ± SEM. $p<0.05$

Effect of an aqueous extract of Velvet Bean on the Superoxide Dismutase (U/mg of tissue)

Figure 8 demonstrates the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) in various Wistar rat groups. Notably, the velvet bean extract and control groups exhibited significantly higher SOD activity when compared to the cadmium only group which was significant ($p<0.05$). Furthermore, the cadmium + velvet bean extract group, showed improved activity when compared to control and velvet bean extract group which was not significant $p<0.05$.

Figure 8: Frontal Cortex of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Activity Level (u/mg of tissue) at the End of Fourth Week. Data are Expressed as Mean ± SEM. $P<0.05$.

Effect of an aqueous extract of Velvet Bean on the Catalase (U/mg of tissue)

Figure 9 shows the activity of catalase in the frontal cortex of various groups of Wistar rats. Notably, the cadmium only group exhibited the lowest catalase activity, while as expected the normal control group exhibited the highest activity. When the cadmium + velvet bean extract group was compared with the normal control group and velvet bean extract only group, there was a statistical significant with ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 9: Frontal Cortex of Catalase (CAT) Activity Level (u/mg of tissue) at the End of Fourth Week. Data are Expressed as Mean \pm SEM. $P < 0.05$

Effects of an aqueous extract of Velvet Bean on the Malondialdehyde (nmol/mg protein)

Figure 10 illustrates catalase activity in the frontal cortex across different groups of Wistar rats. The **cadmium-only group** showed the highest level of Malondialdehyde activity, whereas the **normal control group** recorded the lowest, as anticipated. Comparison between the **cadmium + velvet bean extract group** and both the **normal control** and **velvet bean extract only groups** revealed no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 10: Frontal Cortex of Malondialdehyde (MDA) Activity Level (nmol/mg protein) at the End of Fourth Week. Data are Expressed as Mean \pm SEM. $P < 0.05$

Discussion

Cadmium (Cd) is highly documented as a toxic heavy metal and a widespread environmental contaminant exerting adverse effects on the body metabolism, presenting significant health risks, especially to the nervous system [16]. Cadmium's neurotoxic effects is driven by oxidative stress, neuro-inflammation, and disruption of neuronal integrity which are most severe in the frontal cortex, affecting cognitive and executive functions. [5,17]. Current interventions for cadmium-induced neurotoxicity are limited, often causing significant side effects, and are ineffective in reversing neuronal damage, hence *Mucuna Pruriens* with its bioactive compounds may offer potential benefits in managing cadmium-induced neurotoxicity [17,18].

In this present study the cadmium only demonstrated significant reductions in average weekly body weight from week 2 to week 4 ($p < 0.05$). The weight loss can be attributed to cadmiums oxidative stress due to production of reactive oxygen species which impairs cellular metabolism and promotes muscle and fat stores catabolism [6,19]. Furthermore, cadmium caused reduction in food intake due to cadmium induced anorexia mediated by disruption of hypothalamic appetite regulatory centers [11,20,21]. Interestingly, the velvet bean extract only group demonstrated the highest body weight gain throughout, surpassing even the normal control group, which indicates possible anabolic or nutritive properties of the extract leading to the observed findings., with values comparable to the control group ($p > 0.05$) whose weight is constant and stable as expected due to no treatment intervention. These findings corroborate previous reports indicating that cadmium interferes with metabolic processes, possibly through oxidative stress, suppression of appetite, and disruption of gastrointestinal function, leading to reduced nutrient absorption and energy utilization [15,22,23]. Prolonged cadmium exposure is also known to impair mitochondrial function, thereby reducing ATP production, which is essential for growth and maintenance [22]. Moreover, Velvet bean has been reported to possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and restorative properties, which help counteract cadmium-induced oxidative stress and tissue damage, thus preserving or enhancing body weight [4].

In this study the relative brain weight in cadmium-only group resulted in a significant decline compared to other groups ($p < 0.05$). This decrease in brain weight can be attributed to neurodegeneration, cerebral atrophy, or inhibition of neural cell proliferation due to oxidative stress which damaged the neuronal cells [20]. Cadmium is known to cross the blood-brain barrier and accumulate in brain tissues, leading to oxidative stress, neuronal death, and glial cell dysfunction [17]. Conversely the cadmium + Velvet bean group,

exhibited a less pronounced reduction in brain weight, underscoring the neuroprotective potential of Velvet bean in preserving brain mass possibly through antioxidant mechanisms and inhibition of neuronal apoptosis [12,24].

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) of the frontal cortex of the rats revealed that cadmium only group had numerous necrotic pyramidal cells compared to other groups. This is due the effects of cadmium on the frontal cortex or brain tissue which includes oxidative stress, inflammations and consequent neuronal death. Furthermore, cadmium-only group showed extensive histopathological alterations characterized by widespread necrosis, cytoplasmic *vacuolation*, and nuclear pyknosis. These changes reflect severe cadmium-induced neurotoxicity, as similarly described by [5] and [12], who reported neuronal degeneration and Nissl substance dissolution in cadmium-exposed rodents. However, the cadmium + velvet bean extract group revealed a mixture of necrotic and healthy cells, suggesting partial neuroprotection. This finding suggests that Velvet bean extract partially mitigated cadmium induced. Neurotoxicity due to antioxidants content such as flavonoids which arrested reactive oxygen species and protected neuronal cells from oxidative damage [25].

In this current study Toluidine Blue (TDB) stain of frontal cortex of cadmium only group showed sparsely stained Nissl substance and more necrotic cells when compared to the normal control. This is due to increased ROS as a result of uncontrolled oxidative stress and damage while cadmium + velvet bean extract group showed preserved Nissl substances, some cells were necrotic while others appeared normal. The velvet bean exact was able to achieve these results because they contain high levels of antioxidants(flavonoids, phenols) as shown in this study which assisted in the arrest of reactive oxygen species as well as prevent inflammation of neuronal cells. Conversely in the control and Velvet bean-only groups, the frontal cortex exhibited intact pyramidal neurons with normal morphology and abundant Nissl substance, indicating healthy neuronal function and structural preservation. This observation is in line with previous reports affirming the non-toxic nature of *Mucuna Pruriens* at therapeutic doses [24,25].

Masson's Trichrome staining technique provided insights into extracellular matrix alterations, particularly collagen deposition, which signifies fibrosis. In both the normal control and Velvet Bean-only groups, there was no visible collagen accumulation, affirming the absence of fibrotic activity under physiological and Velvet Bean-treated conditions. Conversely, the cadmium-only group exhibited marked collagen deposition in the frontal cortex, indicating fibrotic remodeling. Fibrosis in neural tissue is often a

consequence of chronic inflammation and unresolved tissue injury, processes frequently instigated by heavy metal toxicity [24]. In the cadmium + Velvet Bean group, the trichrome-stained sections revealed a significant reduction in collagen deposition. This observation reinforces the earlier hypothesis that Velvet Bean extract attenuates inflammatory and fibrotic responses in neural tissue. Such anti-fibrotic effects have been noted in other studies [5, 26].

The PTAH stain revealed a well-organized distribution of pyramidal neurons and astrocytes, indicative of a healthy neuronal microenvironment in the normal control group. This morphological pattern reflects intact neuro-architecture and glial homeostasis. Similarly, the Velvet Bean extract-only group exhibited a comparable histo-architecture, suggesting that the extract alone does not exert harmful effects on cortical tissue. These findings align with previous studies that report *Mucuna Pruriens* as a neuro-restorative agent devoid of histological toxicity [12]. The cadmium-only group demonstrated extensive histological alterations. The most pronounced changes included necrotic pyramidal neurons and an increased presence of astrocytes. The appearance of necrotic neurons indicates direct neurotoxic effects of cadmium, likely mediated through reactive oxygen species (ROS) that induce lipid peroxidation, protein denaturation, and DNA fragmentation [18, 27,28]. The elevated astrocyte count is consistent with *astrogliosis*, a hallmark response to central nervous system injury, which serves as an endogenous attempt at neuroprotection and tissue repair [9,16,29]. The cadmium + Velvet Bean group exhibited a near-normal histological profile, with preserved pyramidal neurons and reduced *astrocytosis*. This suggests that Velvet Bean extract effectively mitigates cadmium-induced neurotoxicity. The neuroprotective potential is likely attributable to its rich content of L-DOPA, polyphenols, and flavonoids, compounds known for their anti-oxidative and anti-inflammatory properties [21].

This study observed cadmium-only group exhibited a notable reduction in GSH levels compared to the control group, indicative of a depleted intracellular redox buffer. Glutathione depletion results from cadmium's high affinity for sulfhydryl groups, leading to GSH oxidation and impaired synthesis [30]. Treatment with Velvet Bean extract elevated GSH levels indicating a reversal of oxidative stress and restoration of cellular redox homeostasis. Interestingly, the velvet bean-only group showed GSH levels comparable to controls, further supporting the antioxidant properties of the extract. These internal comparisons confirm that Velvet Bean effectively mitigates cadmium-induced glutathione depletion. This finding concurs with previous studies by [18, 31], who showed that phytochemicals with thiol-restoring capacities can

replenish GSH pools in toxicological settings. Moreover, [12] reported that *Mucuna Pruriens* improved glutathione levels in oxidative damage models, corroborating the protective effect observed in this study.

Cadmium exposure resulted in a marked reduction in SOD activity compared to the normal control group, underscoring cadmium's suppressive effect on enzymatic antioxidants. SOD catalyzes the dismutation of superoxide radicals into hydrogen peroxide and oxygen; however, cadmium displaces essential metal cofactors in the enzyme's active site, leading to enzyme inactivation [8,32]. Treatment with Velvet Bean significantly restored SOD levels, showing improved antioxidant capacity. The velvet bean-only group maintained nearly normal SOD levels, further suggesting the extract's protective efficacy. Comparing within experimental groups, it is evident that Velvet Bean reversed the cadmium-induced suppression of antioxidant enzymes, reflecting a dose-dependent or combinatorial bioactive effect. These observations are consistent with findings of [16].

Catalase activity in this study significantly declined in cadmium-only rats compared to normal controls, confirming cadmium's ability to impair hydrogen peroxide detoxification [13,33]. This decrease can be attributed to cadmium-mediated inhibition of hem-containing enzymes like catalase, which impairs ROS neutralization and exacerbates oxidative stress. Velvet Bean treatment partially restored catalase levels reflecting the extract's ability to stabilize or enhance enzyme expression or activity. The velvet bean-only group exhibited near-normal catalase activity, further validating its anti-oxidative role. When compared within groups, Velvet Bean treatment showed marked improvement over the cadmium-only group, suggesting potential use in oxidative injury repair. These results are supported by findings from [4, 28,34]. MDA levels increased significantly in the cadmium-only group compared to the normal control, indicating enhanced lipid peroxidation due to cadmium toxicity. MDA, a byproduct of polyunsaturated fatty acid oxidation, serves as a marker of oxidative stress [6]. Cadmium promotes reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation through mitochondrial dysfunction and by inhibiting antioxidant enzymes, leading to membrane lipid peroxidation [15,35]. Notably, the group treated with Velvet Bean extract after cadmium induction showed a substantial reduction in MDA levels (59.8 ± 0.86), suggesting that the extract ameliorates lipid peroxidation. This value was closer to the levels in the velvet bean-only group, highlighting the antioxidant potential of the plant extract. These results align with previous reports from [24,36].

Conclusion

Mucuna Pruriens demonstrated strong ameliorative effects against cadmium-induced frontal cortex injury. These findings support its potential as an affordable, plant based therapeutic agent for preventing or managing heavy metal-induced neurodegeneration. This study also provides a foundation for future clinical investigations on natural neuro-protectants.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts interest.

Funding

We declare that there was no funding for this study

Ethical Considerations

Before commencement of the study ethical approval was obtained from Mulungushi University School of Medicine and Health Sciences ethics committee and National Health Research Authority-Zambia.

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